

Unfazed by the More-Than-Human Face: Renegotiating Progress through Ethical Address

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In this paper, I explore relationships between the human and the more-than-human, and claim that this relationship concerns education in two ways. One way is through the educational possibilities raised by this relationship, and the other is through the ways this relationship will affect the welfare of future generations. To make my claims, I examine and concretize relationships between the human and the more-than-human through arts-based research approach developed through creative writing, via a poem and two pieces of fiction. For clarity, these passages are italicized.

In earlier work, I questioned the human-centeredness of educational becoming. I started with the question posed by Biesta (2014), who asked what it would mean if something “radically different might break through” (p. 49). I chose to connect this question to human relationships with animals, and more specifically, to a relationship with a horse (Hagström, 2016, 2018). In this study, I made a link between the works of Biesta (2015a) and work by Irigaray and Green (2008), a link which I now wish to deepen. Biesta (2015a) emphasized the need to open up to other existential possibilities of ways of being in and with the world. These existential possibilities expose the ways in which we humans must let the world encounter and address us rather than having us see it as an object to be understood. According to Irigaray and Green (2008), education ought to teach how to respect the world and contemplate it. Instead, it has too often been the case that education in Western culture has taught us how to grasp and master the world, according to Irigaray and Green (2008).

While I previously focused on the link between these studies in relation to animals, I now want to expand this idea by having it address the more-than-human. Continuing from the link between the ethical implications for education with regard to respecting it and contemplating it that Irigaray raises and Biesta’s (2015a) thoughts on other existential possibilities, I now connect this link to Biesta’s (2015b) work on whether what we desire in education is, in reality, desirable. Brought together, these arguments invite us to explore and discuss ethics in education in times of transformation such as the current one. I investigate this invitation during a fictional walk in the forest, contemplating whether the more-than-human face can exist, and if it does, how it would appear.

Is it putting my feet down, one after the other, on a bit of mud and grass sticking up in the midst of the slippery ice and creating a little safe spot of grip to keep me going? The melting ice makes it difficult for a two-legged with no grips to get through. Is it the water crossing the path making the ground muddy? Water is rippling across the path, down the slope and then under the snow again, making a trickling sound barely recognizable under the strong wind. Is it the one bare grey juniper sticking out in the

middle of a stand of junipers? Is it the interruption of my steps and train of thought? When and how does a more-than-human face appear? How do they have to merge and crystallize for me to notice? Does it help to lend more-than-human a face? Or does it help more to lend the more-than-human a voice or a sound?

Education Imbued with Imaginaries of Anthropocentrism

Imaginaries of anthropocentrism affect multiple forms of living in ways that might not be desirable, either for themselves or for future generations (in which human generations are included). Building on my earlier research (Hagström, 2016, 2018), I maintain that the question stretches into ecological and ethical dimensions, too. In line with the ecofeminists, as are Adams and Gruen (2014), I argue that it is crucial to simultaneously address questions about ecological, animalist, and feminist issues. Intersectional theorization as a way forward is also highlighted by Calarco (2015).

I call into question how these educational imaginaries, rooted in the idea of human exceptionalism, affect what, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including the human) count as human or non-human. Further, I ask, how do these educational imaginaries affect what, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including that of humans) count as “we,” and what, whose, or how these multiple forms of living (including human living) count in regard to their being ethically taken into consideration. Education and ethics cannot be separated.

The word “unfazed” was chosen for this essay even though, and because, it sounds similar to “face.” It might be heard as *unfaced* with its ‘c’ (unvoiced sibilant /s/) softened to a voiced ‘z,’ and I believe that this thought regarding it is coherent and makes sense in this context, too. But I have chosen “unfazed” with a ‘zed’ because of its meaning of being untouched, unmoved, unruffled, or unworried by the encounter with a more-than-human face.

I argue that because of the anthropocentric imaginaries with which education is imbued, the world is shut out, and multiple forms of living are alienated. Through landslides, wildfires, and storms, the world shouts at us. But as the world is faceless and voiceless, and since we seem to have lost our senses and our sensibility, there are few accessible ways in which it can address us. We remain unfazed by the more-than-human face.

Ethics and Education with and without Faces

In my earlier work (Hagström, 2018), I explored approaches to openness as regards being addressed by the more-than-human. Using the animal ethics of Calarco (2008), I have built on Lévinas’s idea of the face of the Other. I have linked the idea of “being faced by animals” to the horse’s face, which I then extended to the horse’s questioning corporeality (Hagström, 2018). Here, I am pushing this thought of ethical address forward by exploring possibilities for being addressed by multiple forms of living beings.

However, Calarco (2008) presents a perspective in which the ethical address can only appear as a human or animal face, which he presents as “being faced by animals” (p. 63). He argues that animal ethics and environmental ethics are distinct, but complementary. In Calarco’s (2008) critique, I admit, there are connections with acknowledged problems of environmental thought, in

which “environment” becomes a concept that gets generalized too easily, at least with regard to any specific animal. In part, I adhere to this critique because the phenomenon of the more-than-human is multiple in its forms of living. But it hasn’t always had a recognizable face in the world as humans know it. Methodologically, I approach the risk of being “too general,” drawing on Haraway (2008), by emphasizing relations, spaces, and encounters in their specificities.

Why, then, cling to the notion of the face? It is because the notion of the face is connected to the notion of ethical address. It is theoretically embedded into ethics through the work of Lévinas and, further, connected to education through the work of Biesta that builds on Lévinas’s work. Also, building on Lévinas’s work, the face is connected to animal studies through the work of Calarco and others. The question is, without a face, how might it be possible to be addressed by the more-than-human?

Haraway (2008) suggests a priority of vision and the face-to-face when describing relations between humans and animals, specifically in the setting of dogs and agility. Faces may question and address. With horses, there are many possible ways for the face-to-face to occur, but not when riding. And in any relationship with other animals, corporeality is present. As the face asks questions, so may corporeality, as I have argued elsewhere (Hagström, 2018). What the more-than-human has in common with the human is not faces or bodies, but living. And in this living, we are all interdependently connected. This section is followed by a poem:

Seeing an elk seeing me

*fast walk in the forest before dinner
twigs break somewhere
I look around
my feet keep walking on the path*

*my sight is muddled by the dusk
the high grass is yellowish grey
the sky is grey, the fir trees are black
the grey cliffs are high*

*still as the cliff, still as the sky and the fir trees
an elk is seeing me, I stop and*

*start fiddling with the high grass
hoping the elk stays on for a bit*

*I move around a little, glancing towards the elk
who is still seeing me*

*the yellowish grey grass is high
the sky is grey, the fir trees are black
the high cliffs are grey*

*the elk turns around
climbs up the cliff, disappears in the woods*

my sight is muddled by the dusk

On the More-Than-Human

Furry and four-legged, elks bear similarities to horses. This may imply that they would emerge more prominently for me in a text, given the context of my previous research. Also, the eyes, nostrils and mouth on an elk's head form a recognizable face. But the elk's appearing and disappearing in this piece points to a merging of life and living in various forms, such as the fir trees, the grass, and the "I."

From this point on, I want to highlight the more-than-human, and to do so, I will start out with Haraway (2008). Haraway (2008, p. 341) acknowledges the adoption of the locution "more-than-human" from van Dooren's work *Seeding Property: Nature, Human/Plant Relations and the Production of Wealth* (2007). In Haraway's work, the notion comes into play in an aside during the sharing of stories about dog breeding:

Discovery of gold radically and permanently changed the food economy, species assemblages, politics, human and *more-than-human* [emphasis added] demographics, and natural social ecology of California and other parts of the North American West. (Haraway, 2008, p. 101)

Haraway (2008) maintains that the stories she presents regarding dogs need to be told in order to tease out the "personal and collective response required now, not centuries ago" (p. 97). According to Haraway (2008), "Companion species cannot afford evolutionary, personal or historical amnesia" (p. 98).

I follow the track from Haraway's use of "more-than-human" via van Dooren's (2007) work, which links to Curry (2008). I'll start out with the work of Curry, then return to van Doreen.

Curry (2008) maintains that "an inclusive ecocentrism is impossible to envisage without recognizing and appreciating our immersion in this vast and intricate discursivity, the more-than-(but including)-human" (p. 59). He maintains that this thought builds upon Gregory Bateson's work on how mind and nature form a "necessary unity." Also, Curry (2008) brings forth the idea that this concept has been furthered in ecological-phenomenological terms by Abram and in ecofeminist terms by Plumwood. Curry (2008) argues for a relational pluralism that is necessarily ecocentric. He contrasts ecocentrism with anthropocentrism, stating that ecocentrism "locates value and/or agency within nature as such, including (but not limited to) humanity: what David Abram aptly calls a 'more-than-human world'" (p. 54). Curry (2008) continues, "As part of such a project, right thinking can help to clear a space for a different mode which is better able to apprehend and appreciate the intrinsic value of more-than-human nature, or rather wildness (including human)" (p. 64).

The formulation of the more-than-(but including)-human (Curry 2008, p. 59) is what van Dooren (2009) built upon when further developing his work on banking seeds and the conservation of agricultural diversity, in which he concluded, “banking well is about banking in and with more-than-human communities. It is about imagining and conserving biosocial natures through a sharing of diversities” (p. 390). In van Dooren’s work, the “more-than-human” becomes important because “it describes communities and places in which human projects and desires are not completely dominant” (2009, p. 375). Further, according to van Dooren (2009), “These are multi-species communities in which a space is held open for other organisms to live and possibly even flourish” (p. 375). This offers us a view where the *more-than-human* embraces humans, but where there are more beings than just humans. I want to emphasize the connection of these insights to education through the care for future generations of more-than-(but including)-human life through the banking of seeds and the subsequent conservation of agricultural diversity.

Van Dooren (2009) also draws from the work of Plumwood in order to criticize the instrumentalization of non-humans, in which “one ... attaches no real or essential value to their living for their own sake, or to the broader relationships that comprise agricultural environments” (p. 380). This brings forth a critique of a “reductionist and economically convenient understanding of ‘nature’” (van Dooren, 2009).

Through elks, dog breeding, and seeds, I have highlighted the notion of the more-than-human. In the following section, I’ll focus on the connection with the face.

Dressing up the More-Than-Human with a Face

Imaginations of anthropocentrism show themselves through the desire of humans to recognize and prioritize faces. But then again, not each and every human face is equally recognized and prioritized.

The more-than-human might or might not present a face. This leads to the question of whether the more-than-human needs to be lent a face or dressed up with a face to be rendered visible.

One example is the Swedish fictional figure *Skogsmulle*, created in the 1950s by the Swedish non-profit NGO *Swedish Outdoor Association* (Friluftsrämjandet, 2024). This organization disseminates knowledge on *The Right of Public Access*, a right protecting public access to nature, recognized in the Swedish constitution. *Skogsmulle* is a character used in teaching materials meant to help children learn about nature. This figure, two-legged, with arms, face, and a tail, and with a specific greeting phrase, is widely known in the Swedish context and used in formal and informal outdoor education. (This name also carries an inferred connotation signifying people who love and care for the forest, sometimes in a derogatory sense.)

What I wish to highlight here by paying attention to *Skogsmulle* is the apparent need and desire to present a human face with two eyes above a nose in order to be addressed and to be able to respond to the address. Maybe this manner of conjuring a face, calling out “*Kollikok!*” from the forest, is helpful for humans in being able to extend concerns about the other. Sometimes, dressing up the more-than-human with a face may be helpful, although there is a deep risk of erasing the specificity of how the more-than-human, with or without a face, might exist. Further, it is not at all helpful

when humans mix up their own needs, wishes, and desires with those of the other, which has its own needs, wishes, and desires.

I will now leave the two eyes above a nose behind, and instead of a *face*, I will pay attention to *someplace*, or more specifically, to how the being addressed by the more-than-human in its specificities may break through. The face, or rather place, has no nose here, but the ethics of the face remains in terms of its being questioned through the address by the more-than-human. This section is followed by a piece of fiction.

Someplace

I leave the forest lane, which is wet and muddy due to wheel tracks, and I turn in on a dry and very small track. Here, it's not a forest, really, but rather a fir tree farm. This part of the woods consists of narrow and strict rows of fir trees, where the sun can't reach to the lower branches. They're all brown, edgy and give me scratches.

For me, this is the only way possible to enter this impervious part of the woods. As I follow this straight line, other small paths emerge in various directions. One of them is spacious enough to let me come through. I climb over a fallen fir tree. I raise my eyes, and there's light between the dead branches. A clearing opens up, and I enter.

The sunshine is reflected on the grey granite and makes the high yellow grass translucent. Big stones are toppling over and around each other. I'm enclosed by high fir trees.

From here, I can see how the upper branches facing the sun are green. I turn around to look towards the sun. Little gnats twirl around in the air. I stand still, and I feel that this is someplace. How come this isn't just somewhere, but someplace?

Days pass. I want to find that someplace again. This time, I approach the entrance in the narrow fir tree rows from the opposite direction, reminding myself that the hunting tower should be opposite the track's entrance and the small meadow should be only a short distance away. At this point, I find a narrow line and start to follow it.

But where are the paths trodden by deer and martens, showing ways other than the human-made mechanical track, yet too impenetrable for me to follow? That fallen fir tree that stopped me in my tracks, with the green color standing out amongst brown branches, where is it?

I see a few stones, but the sunshine isn't reflected on a big piece of granite. Instead, the granite is covered with moss. Disappointment hits me. Am I too eager to find it again, so that it's no longer waiting for me? I enter the clearing. I cross over the moss and turn myself towards the sun. I look in various directions, but it doesn't look the same. I wait.

The sun glitters on a little granite stone. It's formed like the back of a sofa with the soft moss as a seat, inviting me to sit down. I sit and see that there are heathers popping out of the moss.

Willow warblers, wrens and blackbirds all are singing. I hear noises of twigs breaking. I feel the presence of the elks, the deer and the foxes, but I don't see any of them with my eyes.

This isn't somewhere; this is someplace.

After I have left the sunny stone and warm moss sofa and walked a few steps further into the woods, I realize that this wasn't someplace. Now, I see in front of me a big section of granite, scratches from deer in the moss and toppling stones. Also, a bit to the left, a fallen fir tree with a crown of green color stands out amongst the brown branches. My senses reorient my position. If this is someplace, then, what was the other place?

Desirability in and of Education

Grasping and mastering, on the one hand, and respecting and contemplating, on the other hand, intermingle when the addressing breaks through. For Irigaray and Green (2008), respecting and contemplating would be desirable in education.

Further, from the angle of Biesta (2015b), the question is whether what we desire in and from education is, in actuality, desirable. As Biesta (2015b) pointed out, “We want teachers to open up new vistas, new opportunities, and help children and young people to interrogate whether what they say they want or desire is actually what they should desire” (p. 82).

If the emphasis were instead to be put on respecting and contemplating the world rather than on grasping and mastering it, then a renegotiation would be needed, one in which value would not be primarily economical and measured in economic growth. The values in the exploitation of natural resources need to be replaced by the contemplation of what values are desirable. Counting and measuring are all well and very helpful, in many ways. In context, for instance, the measuring of global warmth is crucial for rendering visible the magnitude of the climate crisis.

Put into the context of what is desirable for education in a more-than-human world, a renegotiation of economic growth and of social justice for the currently living and future generations would be needed. I wish to invite all of us to think about how human senses have been distorted in their relationship to anthropocentric imaginaries. I argue that the distortion of human senses has led to a bereavement of sensing when it is addressed by the more-than-human. The grasping and mastering of the world do not intermingle with, but rather fully outweigh, respect for and contemplation of the world.

Renegotiation of Progress

I started from the idea that education is imbued with anthropocentric imaginaries. I continued through with a linking from my previous research (Hagström, 2016, 2018) of Irigaray's (Irigaray

& Green, 2008) ethical implications for education to Biesta's (2015a) thoughts on other existential possibilities. I then explored this angle further by connecting it to Biesta's (2015b) questioning of whether what we desire is, in reality, desirable in education. In order to address this last question, I steered the discussion into focusing on progress.

I would argue that within anthropocentric imaginaries, progress gets caught up in becoming focused on the more, the bigger, the stronger, and the faster. One might consider each of these better, but for what or whom? Progress gets distorted and confused with economic growth. Progress, which is central to any relation to education, needs to be renegotiated in order to make it more fully educational.

In relation to this discussion, I have chosen to introduce Nisbet's (1994) work on the history of the idea of progress in relation to Dewey's (1916) article "Progress." The idea of progress is a powerful motivator in Western history, as Nisbet (1994) points out, because the idea brings together the past, the present, and the future. Nisbet (1994) implies that the idea of progress is not just desirable, but also possibly a historical necessity, even something close to a law of nature. Dewey (1916) affirms the idea that humans may wish to believe in this idea of the historical inevitability of progress, saying, "We [have] confused rapidity of change with advance, and we [have taken] certain gains in our own comfort and ease as signs that cosmic forces [are] working inevitably to improve the whole state of human affairs" (p. 312). Here, Dewey invokes cosmic forces, although this passage might be read as having an undertone of a *laissez-faire* attitude in that humans read the signs in ways that are most convenient for them. A main point for Dewey (1916) is that progress is something that should not be taken for granted by humans, but inevitably seems to be taken this way: "Progress is not automatic; it depends upon human intent and aim and upon acceptance of responsibility for its production" (p. 315). What Dewey (1916) brings forth is the concept of responsibility. This is not a given, and I claim that it is at risk of being ignored.

If progress is a dogma that holds Western civilization back, as Nisbet (1994) affirmatively states, then there might be a need to take a closer look at whether this dogma is desirable in and for education in a time of transformation such as we are facing now.

While Dewey (2016) emphasizes the need for intelligence, I think that in combination with intelligence, our senses and sensibility need to be affirmed. To do this, we must constantly renegotiate the anthropocentric imaginaries that dominate the imaginaries of education.

It might be time to return to how the imaginaries of progress play out when joining forces with anthropocentrism, as well as with economization, and what might be lost to progress in relation to education. Humans need to accept responsibility for the production of progress, as Dewey (1916) points out. The connection to responsibility potentially makes an emphasis on progress more educational, I would argue, because it brings forth the connection between ethics and education. Progress without responsibility is not desirable in, of, or for itself, or for education. If progress is pursued without responsibility, it renders visible the ways that these anthropocentric imaginaries affect what, which, whose, and/or how multiple forms of living are included in what is counted as "we." This means that it affects what, which, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including human living) are being taken into account ethically. This distinction cuts through living in various contexts, splitting life from death.

Concluding Remarks

In this paper, I explored and discussed relationships between the human and the more-than-human. To do this, I articulated and concretized relationships between the human and the more-than-human through arts-based research in the form of creative writing, incorporating into the study a poem and two pieces of fiction about an elk, walks, and places in the forest. The more-than-human, of course, includes more than elks and forests, but as my methodological promise was to meet the risk of environmental ethics by being too general, drawing on Haraway (2008), I chose to concretize relationships to elks and forests in their specificities through the poem and the pieces of fiction. My intent here was to bring the reader to share these experiences in a concrete way and, further, to explore the themes within the pieces themselves, and continue the discussion on the themes of this paper in relation to the thinkers I have mentioned.

To conclude, I claim, first, that by being miseducated into over-focusing on grasping and mastering the world, human life has been led into being continuously unfazed by the more-than-human face. And second, I claim that there is still hope as regards changing this situation.

I argue that this hope concerns education in two ways. One way is with regard to the educational possibility of being addressed by the more-than-human, and the other way is with regard to the care for future generations.

Regarding the educational possibilities, instead of focusing only on being addressed by the human *face*, I paid attention to *someplace*. The piece of fiction called *Someplace*, as well as the fictional walk and the poem interlinking an elk, trees, grass and the “I,” concern this. Building on Biesta’s (2015a) work on “being addressed or being spoken to by what or who is other” (p. 239), I argue that it is the task of education to form our human senses so that they address the times when multiple forms of living address us. This may break through in the form of a *someplace*, in which I, with the senses and sensibility I have available, may be spoken to both within and beyond human language. If this address were only provided via human faces, then humans would suffer from a deprivation of sense and sensibility. This recognition reconnects us to what was discussed above, namely, who is counted as a “we.” Who, of all living beings, including humans, is being ethically taken into account? This question ultimately creates a division between the currently living and a full consideration of both the living and the dead.

The insight leads to another perspective that concerns education, which involves care for future generations. If progress is pursued within the anthropocentric imaginaries with which education is imbued, without taking responsibility for and/or without paying attention to caring for life, then this approach, too, separates the now-living from the combined world of life and death. It splits human suffering and death right here and now as regards the consequences of the climate crisis, which is creating a level of suffering and death that we keep on giving to future generations.

As a human endeavor, education builds upon hope for future generations. As Dewey (1916) accurately stated more than 100 years ago, raising a perspective I agree with, we have confused rapidity of change with advancement. This confusion is not desirable. We desire progress in terms of rapidity of change rather than paying attention to what kind of progress we should desire.

Humans might come to their senses if they are addressed by the more-than-human. In this confrontation, educational possibilities might arise through a renegotiation of the ways progress might exist. In order to renegotiate progress, it is necessary to loosen the anthropocentric shackles of the imaginaries and the practices of continuous rapid growth and attend instead to our responsibility for the productions of progress. In communities including the more-than-human (van Dooren, 2009, p. 390), or multi-species communities (van Dooren, 2009, p. 375), space for *other* living organisms is held open in order for them to flourish. As Haraway (2008) argues, there is a need for personal and collective response, and companion species cannot afford “evolutionary, personal or historical amnesia” (p. 98). Progress, in its educational sense, embraces an interlinked past, present and future, foregrounding intergenerational relations. Such relations are built upon care and hope for future generations within more-than-human communities.

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